

A NOTE ON THE PROPERTIES OF SODIUM HYPONITRITE

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Oza (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 225) has reported the properties and preparation of sodium hyponitrite and showed the existence of a tri-hydrate. The present author has investigated in great detail the properties of hyponitrites (Partington and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2071 ; 1932, 2589). There is nothing new in the properties described by Oza. The hydrated salt has not even been analysed, both in his previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1944, 21, 70) and in the present paper. The present paper only gives the loss in weight. Probably it is assumed that the loss is due to water, inspite of the author's statement on page 77 of the first paper.

The present author has prepared large quantities of hyponitrites and he feels that it is not necessary to bubble nitrogen during reduction. The gases evolved in the flask protect the liquid from atmospheric CO_2 . As mentioned however by him, nitrogen should be passed during the filtration of the product.

Oza has analysed $\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ by a volumetric method which is unpublished. The author feels that it is not possible to *accurately* determine hyponitrite by any volumetric method due to the great instability of its solution inspite of Oza's observation on the effect of CO_2 on it.

As regards the action of potassium iodide, the author would refer to page 2072 of his first paper. I do not think Oza has any thing more to add.

Oza in his first paper has studied the thermal decomposition giving the furnace temperature for the decomposition temperature of the salt. The furnace temperature is bound to be higher. He complains that the author did not give any analytical results. They can be found on page 2077 of the first paper. Oza mentions the presence of nitric oxide in the gaseous product but does not mention it in the analysis.

Oza has not given any more information on the properties of hyponitrites than those contained in our papers.

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